

Factors Influencing Governance And Organizational Sustainability

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to identify factors influencing sustainability governance and to assess the effectiveness of sustainable governance strategies from economic, social, and environmental perspectives. Using a literature review methodology, this study collects and analyzes articles from leading academic databases, with selection criteria involving relevance to the theme of sustainability. The analysis results show that sustainability governance is influenced by various internal and external factors. Internal factors include diverse board composition, visionary leadership, effective sustainability management systems, supportive organizational culture, and transparency in information disclosure. External factors encompass regulatory pressures, industry norms, market demand, availability of technology, and social and political contexts. The study also highlights the importance of strategies and practices such as integrating sustainability into business strategies, Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) disclosures, stakeholder engagement, and business model innovation to support sustainable governance.

Keywords: Sustainability governance, sustainability management system, organizational culture, business model innovation

INTRODUCTION

Sustainability governance is becoming increasingly important at all levels, from global to local, influenced by a number of main factors. On a global scale, the climate crisis is forcing demands for more sustainable action from businesses and governments, while increasing inequality and environmental degradation emphasize the need for inclusive development and protection of ecosystems (Van Niekerk, 2020). At the regional level, the emergence of new regulations related to sustainability as well as pressure from consumers who are increasingly aware of environmental impacts is driving the need for the implementation of strong

Governance by businesses (Sajjad et al., 2020). This not only ensures regulatory compliance and builds customer trust, but also improves Governance's competitiveness and profitability. At the local level, the importance of Governance is reflected in the sustainable management of natural resources, managing the social impact of business, and building community resilience to climate change and natural disasters (Imperiale & Vanclay, 2021). Overall, the implementation of strong Governance is key in ensuring a sustainable future for and for society, contributing to solving global challenges and creating new opportunities for economic growth and social development. Therefore, investment in Governance is critical for a sustainable future.

On the other hand, sustainability governance, a concept that links environmental and social problems with effective decision-making processes, has undergone an interesting transformation in both academic literature and industrial practice (Scholz, 2017). Companies are expected to reduce damage to the environment around their operations, but this still continues to happen. Over time, perspectives related to the environment, social and economy began to change in society to begin to strive for continuous development and improvement in a sustainable manner. This change is reflected in the increasing prominence of frameworks such as ESG (Environmental, Social and Governance) investing, which considers a company's performance across these three pillars (Hoang, 2018).

However, previous research on sustainability governance has also revealed several challenges. One of the main obstacles is that the definition and measurement of progress is still ambiguous. The concept of "sustainable" is contextual, making comparisons across industries or regions complicated. Integrating sustainability goals into existing governance structures is complex, requiring transformation of corporate culture and decision-making processes. Balancing short-term profits with long-term sustainability goals is also a dilemma for many companies. Broadly, governance refers to the systems and processes that guide decision making within an organization, country, or even global scale. Its scope includes formal rules and regulations, as well as informal norms and values. In the context of sustainability, effective governance ensures that these systems take into account the long-term well-being of the environment and society, along with economic viability.

On the other hand, "sustainability" is a multidimensional concept that refers to practices that meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs, taking into account the balance between economic, social and environmental aspects. The economic dimension refers to practices that meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their needs. Social sustainability focuses on creating fair and equal conditions for all members of society. The environmental dimension emphasizes protecting ecosystems and natural resources for future

generations.

This paper aims to identify factors that influence sustainability in governance and assess the effectiveness of sustainable governance strategies from an economic, social and environmental perspective. Through a comprehensive literature review, researchers are expected to make a valuable contribution to the effective implementation of sustainable governance strategies. It is hoped that the results of this research will provide valuable insights for organizations or business actors who are trying to achieve sustainability within their governance framework.

THEORITICAL REVIEW

Governance is often discussed as a tool, but in the context of GCG (Good Corporate Governance), governance is referred to as corporate governance (Syahlian, 2024). According to the Turnbull Report, governance is a company's internal management system whose main aim is to reduce risks to achieve business goals through managing company assets and increasing equity investment in short-term bonds. The Corporate Governance Association in Malaysia, namely the Finance Committee on Corporate Governance (FCCG), defines corporate governance as the processes and structures used to manage and develop business operations and company activities with the aim of increasing business growth and profitability (Asmara, 2017). Apart from that, several management organizations have mentioned management, coaching, administration, administration, leadership, and so on (Mubarok, 2019). However, this statement is not completely accurate.

Governance theory is a concept that refers to the ways in which organizations or institutions are regulated, guided and supervised, including aspects of decision making, transparency, accountability, internal control and compliance with regulations. Some of the main theories in governance include Agency Theory explained by Jensen and Meckling (1976), which describes the relationship between owners (principals) and managers (agents) as well as mechanisms for reducing conflicts of interest through incentives and monitoring. Stewardship Theory by Donaldson and Davis (1991) states that managers are motivated to act in the best interests of owners and organizations through high trust relationships. Stakeholder Theory by Freeman (1984) emphasizes the importance of considering the interests of all stakeholders, including employees, customers and communities, not just shareholders. Resource Dependence Theory by Pfeffer and Salancik (1978) focuses on how organizations manage their dependence on external resources to reduce dependency and increase control over critical resources. These figures have made major contributions to the development of governance theory, providing important insights for understanding how organizations can be managed better and more responsibly.

Governance Sustainability

Governance Sustainability is a management approach that integrates economic, social and environmental considerations in organizational or entity decision making. Its core principles include transparency, accountability, participation, sustainability, and ethics and integrity, ensuring that business practices support a long-term balance between economic interests and planetary sustainability and social well-being.

Major figures in this field include Elinor Ostrom (1990) published "Governing the Commons: The Evolution of Institutions for Collective Action" and received the Nobel Prize in Economics (2009) for her theory of the management of common resources; John Elkington (1994) developed the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) concept in his book "Cannibals with Forks: The Triple Bottom Line of 21st Century Business"; and Michael Porter, who together with Kramer (2011) introduced the concept of Creating Shared Value (CSV) in the article "Creating Shared Value" in the Harvard Business Review. Andrew J. Hoffman and Robert G. Eccles contributed to the integration of environmental issues into business strategy and transparent sustainability reporting, respectively with publications such as "From Heresy to Dogma: An Institutional History of Corporate Environmentalism" (2001) and "The Integrated Reporting Movement: Meaning, Momentum, Motives, and Materiality" (2014). Herman Daly, with his work "Steady-State Economics" (1977), emphasized the importance of sustainable economic growth within ecological constraints. Practical implementation of these principles by global companies.

This study also used a systematic literature review and bibliometric analysis (Bartolini et al., 2019; Huang et al., 2020). The protocol stages used as a basis or guide are the PRISMA Protocol, which consists of identification, screening, and inclusion (Page et al., 2021). The bibliometric analysis procedure starts from determining research objectives, formulating research questions, and formulating search strategies to collect datasets (Huang et al., 2020). This study combines the systematic stages of SLR and bibliometric analysis because they have similar procedures starting from determining research objectives, formulating research questions, developing search strategies for data collection, and conducting analysis with VosViewer.

LITERATURE DATABASE

Search results for articles from the Google, Scencedirect, and Emerald literature databases according to the keywords "Governance Sustainability", "Sustainability", "Corporate" obtained 105 articles (published in 2012-2024) consisting of:

- 1) 40 accessible articles
- 2) 20 articles that match the subject areas "Corporate Sustainability" and "Corporate Management".
- 3) 21 articles with document types "article research" and "literature review"

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4) 34 articles in Indonesian and English

5) 34 articles in Indonesian and English that have been published will be collected and screened for the next stage.

Screening articles are filtered by checking the entire text that corresponds to the research subject. From the 34 selected articles, 23 articles were used for this research. Therefore, based on the research methodology taken from 115 identified research articles, 23 relevant research articles were obtained which were used as literature review studies with the flowchart presented below.

Figure 1. PRISMA flowchart for research data processing

The 23 articles were followed by analysis using VosViewer. Network visualization is used to explore research on character education, including recent developments and previous research. In network visualization, interrelated terms are presented based on previous studies. The visualization consists of 9 clusters, 92 items, and 92 links. The different colors in Figure 2 indicate clusters of terms, with the most dominant records displayed in the largest nodes. VosViewer makes it easy for readers to observe these visualizations. As for the results of VosViewer research related to Governance Sustainability.

Figure 2. Visualization Based on VosViewer

Based on the results of his study from 23 studies published from 2012-2024. The following is a summary of the research study presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Results of Previous Research Studies 2012 - 2024

No.	Research Name (Year)	Research Topics	Research Scope	Methodology	Research result
1	Hussain et al. (2018)	The Relationship between Corporate Governance and Sustainability Performance of Tripple Bottom Line	Company in the United States	Content analysis of sustainability reports using the Global Reporting Initiative framework	Certain corporate governance mechanisms influence profit, environmental and social performance differently. Existing theories need to be developed to explain which dimensions of sustainability are more affected by corporate governance.
2	Prno & Slocombe (2012)	Social License to Operate in the Mining Sector	Mining in Northern Canada	Case study use governance and sustainability theory	Local communities are important actors in the sustainability of mining projects. Mining companies need social permission from communities to operate.
3	Michelon & Parbonetti (2012)	Board of Directors Composition, Leadership, and Sustainability Disclosure	Companies in the United States and Europe	Data analysis of board of directors characteristics and corporate sustainability disclosures	Board composition Good directors influence the company's sustainability disclosure.
4	Bowen et al. (2017)	Governance Challenges for Achieving Sustainable Development Goals	-	Literature Review	Three governance challenges for the SDGs: (1) collective action across sectors and scales, (2) fair and equitable decision making and (3)

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					accountability mechanisms for societal actors.
5	Husted & Sousa-Filho (2016)	Sustainability Project Governance and ESG Performance	Companies in 9 countries	Data analysis uses hierarchical linear and regression models	Collaborative governance of sustainability projects produces the highest ESG performance, followed by internal, and lastly outsourcing. A country's stakeholder orientation influences this relationship.
6	Albitar et al. (2012)	ESG Disclosure and Company Performance Before and After Integrated Reporting	FTSE 350 (UK) companies between 2009 and 2018	Data analysis uses a regression model	There is a positive relationship between ESGD scores and company performance before and after 2013. Corporate governance mechanisms influence the ESGD relationship with company performance. Companies that implement integrated reporting voluntarily tend to have better financial performance.

7	Alsayegh (2020)	ESG Disclosure and Corporate Sustainability Performance in Asia	Companies in Asia between 2005 and 2017		<p>Good disclosure of ESG information has a positive effect on a company's economic, environmental and social sustainability performance.</p> <p>Environmental and social performance has a positive influence on the company's economic performance.</p>
8	Bolton & Hannon (2016)	Innovative Business Models for Socio-Technical System Transformation	Decentralized energy technology in the UK		<p>Innovative business models play a role in the development and implementation of sustainable technologies.</p> <p>A systems-based approach is needed to analyze business models in a socio-technical context.</p>

9	Lange et al. (2013)	A Framework for Understanding Modes of Sustainable Development Governance	-	Meta-analysis of existing frameworks for sustainable development governance	A multi-dimensional approach that considers political processes (politics), institutional structures (polity), and policy content (policy) is needed to understand the complexity of sustainable development governance.
10	Klettner et al (2014)	Sustainability Governance in Large Australian Companies	Large companies listed in Australia	Empirical analysis of the annual and sustainability reports of 50 large Australian companies	Major Australian companies are showing progress in integrating sustainability into core business operations. Leadership structures and clear communication about sustainability are evidence of its implementation.
11	Rodriguez-Fernandez (2016)	Reciprocal Relationship Between Corporate Social Responsibility and Financial Performance	The company is listed on the Madrid Stock Exchange	Theoretical and empirical studies use social behavior indices to measure CSR	There is a positive reciprocal relationship between CSR and financial performance. Investments in social policies can increase a company's financial resources and vice versa.
12	Voegtlin & Scherer (2017)	Governance Scheme for Responsible Innovation	-	Global Governance Scheme for Responsible Innovation Discussion of	A deliberation-based continuity management scheme is needed to encourage innovation that avoids damage and

				the global governance scheme for responsible innovation	provides benefits for sustainable development.
13	Naciti (2019)	Composition of the Board of Directors and Company Sustainability Performance	Multinational companies in 46 countries	Data analysis from 362 The company uses a two-step systematic common moment estimation method	Diverse board composition and separation of chairman and CEO roles are associated with higher corporate sustainability performance.
14	Glass et al. (2016)	The Impact of Women Leaders on Corporate Environmental Strategy	All Fortune 500 CEOs and board directors for ten years	Data analysis of women's leadership at the CEO, board of directors level, and its cumulative effect	Companies with gender diverse leadership are more effective in implementing environmentally friendly strategies.
15	Amran et al. (2013)	The Role of the Board of Directors in the Quality of Sustainability Reporting in the Asia-Pacific	Company in 12 countries in Asia-Pacific	Cross-sectional study of 113 companies	The quality of sustainability reporting in Asia-Pacific still needs to be improved. Corporate social responsibility (TJSP) values embedded in the company's vision and mission have been proven to improve the quality of sustainability reporting.

16	Patterson et al. (2017)	Governance and Politics of Transformation Towards Sustainability	-	A critical review of four approaches to understanding transformation towards sustainability	Governance and politics play an important role in the transformation towards sustainability. Future research needs to focus on developing a more robust framework for understanding this transformation.
17	Baumgartner & Rauter (2016)	Integrating Sustainability into Business Strategy	-	Literature review	Discusses three complementary dimensions of strategic management to integrate sustainability issues into corporate activities and strategies: strategy process, strategy content, and strategy context.
18	Buallay (2018)	The Relationship Between ESG Disclosure and Bank Performance	235 banks worldwide for 10 years (2007-2016)	Data analysis uses regression	There is a positive relationship between ESG disclosure with bank performance. Environmental disclosure has a positive impact on ROA and TQ, while corporate social responsibility disclosure has a negative impact on the three performance models. Corporate governance disclosure has a negative impact on ROA and ROE, but positive on Tobin's Q.

19	Garcia et al. (2017)	ESG Performance in BRICS Companies from Sensitive Industries	365 companies registered with BRICS between 2010 and 2012	Panel data analysis uses linear regression	Firms in sensitive industries have better environmental performance, even when controlling for firm size and country.
20	Dremptic et al. (2017)	The Impact of ESG Ratings on Sustainable and Responsible Investment	The company whose data rated by Thomson Reuters ASSET4 ESG	Data analysis using correlation	There is a significant positive correlation between the variables mentioned. Larger companies with more resources tend to have better ESG ratings. This raises questions about the accuracy of ESG ratings in assessing a company's sustainability performance.
21	Xie et al. (2017)	The Relationship Between ESG Disclosure and Corporate Efficiency	-	Data envelopment analysis	ESG information disclosure has a positive relationship with company efficiency at moderate disclosure levels. Disclosure of governance information has the strongest positive relationship with corporate efficiency, followed by disclosure of social and environmental information.

22	Ben-Amar et al. (2015)	The Role of Women on the Board of Directors and Climate Change Disclosure	Public companies in Canada between 2008-2014	Data analysis uses regression	The probability of voluntary climate change disclosure increases as the percentage of women on the board of directors increases.
23	Frantzeskaki & Loorbach (2012)	Governance Towards a Sustainability Transition	-	Literature review	Examining the tension between sustainability target setting and governance efforts. Suggests transition management as a governance approach that can address these tensions through selective participatory processes of visualizing, negotiating, learning, and experimenting.

Governance Sustainability Dimensions

Sustainability governance involves various aspects that ensure that policies, practices and processes within an organization or government support long-term sustainability. This dimension of sustainability governance aims to create a framework that enables organizations to operate responsibly and sustainably, ensuring that business practices are not only economically profitable but also provide long-term social and environmental benefits. In the literature on sustainability governance, several dimensions have been identified:

1. Economic Dimension

Covers aspects such as corporate financial performance, long-term value creation, and integration of sustainability into business strategy. Baumgartner & Rauter (2016) observed the relationship between corporate sustainability management and value creation.

2. Environmental Dimensions

Focus on the company's environmental performance, including the ecological impact of operations and environmental strategy. Glass et al. (2016) explored the impact of

female leaders on corporate environmental strategy.

3. Social Dimension

Includes corporate social responsibility, engagement with local communities, and social justice. Rodriguez-Fernandez (2016) investigated the reciprocal relationship between corporate social responsibility and financial performance.

4. Dimensions of Corporate Governance

Includes governance structures and mechanisms that govern corporate behavior in terms of sustainability, such as the composition of the board of directors and disclosure practices. Michelon & Parbonetti (2012) and Lange et al. (2013) investigated the relationship between the composition of the board of directors and corporate sustainability disclosures.

5. Policy and Political Dimensions

Covers the role of governance and politics in supporting or hindering transformation towards sustainability. Patterson et al. (2017) consider the role of governance and politics in the transformation towards sustainability.

6. Dimensions of Innovation and Transformation

Investigates how innovation can lead to sustainable development and how socio-technical transformation processes can be leveraged to achieve these goals. Bolton & Hannon (2016) and Frantzeskaki & Loorbach (2012) discuss this.

Each of these dimensions is interrelated and influences each other, so a holistic and integrative approach is essential to achieving true sustainability goals.

STRATEGY AND PRACTICE

Strategies and practices to support sustainability in governance have been a focus in the literature with a variety of approaches. First, the integration of sustainability into business strategy, such as strategic sustainability management and the development of innovative business models, has become a priority (Baumgartner & Rauter, 2016). Furthermore, effective corporate governance, such as a diverse board of directors composition, female leadership, and ESG disclosure, is recognized as a key factor in improving sustainability performance (Naciti, 2019). In addition, accountability and transparency, such as through sustainability reporting and climate change disclosure, are also important in demonstrating a company's commitment to sustainability (Michelon & Parbonetti, 2012; Ben-Amar et al., 2015).

Stakeholder engagement, such as obtaining social permission to operate and implementing transition management, is also recognized as a key element in strengthening sustainability (Prno & Slocombe, 2012; Frantzeskaki & Loorbach, 2012). Furthermore, governance frames of reference, including multi-dimensional frameworks and global governance schemes, are considered important for understanding system complexity and encouraging responsible

innovation (Lange et al., 2013; Voegtlin & Scherer, 2017). However, there are challenges that need to be overcome, such as achieving sustainable development goals (SDGs) and strengthening existing frames of reference (Bowen et al., 2017; Patterson et al., 2017). By implementing these strategies and practices effectively, organizations can achieve their sustainability goals and contribute to a more sustainable future.

However, there are challenges that need to be addressed, such as achieving the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and strengthening existing frameworks of reference to remain relevant in the face of growing sustainability challenges (Bowen et al., 2017; Patterson et al., 2017). By implementing these strategies and practices effectively, organizations can achieve their sustainability goals and contribute to a more sustainable future. This approach not only helps reduce negative impacts on the environment and society but also improves the company's reputation and competitiveness in the global market.

Key Success Factors for Government Sustainability

Based on the research that has been reviewed, there are several key factors that are considered to influence the success or failure of sustainability governance which are presented as follows

a. Internal Factors:

- Composition of the board of directors

A diverse and independent board of directors, with a strong commitment to sustainability, can drive better decision making and increase accountability (Hussain et al., 2018; Michelon & Parbonetti, 2012; Naciti, 2019).

- Leadership:

Leadership that is visionary and committed to sustainability can inspire and mobilize organizations to achieve sustainability goals (Glass et al., 2016).

- Sustainability management

An effective sustainability management system can help organizations to monitor, measure and improve their sustainability performance (Baumgartner & Rauter, 2016).

- Organizational culture

An organizational culture that supports sustainability can encourage employees to behave and make decisions in a sustainable way (Husted & Sousa-Filho, 2016).

- Disclosure of information

Transparent and comprehensive disclosure of sustainability information can increase accountability and attract investors and other stakeholders (Albitar et al., 2018; Buallay, 2018; Xie et al., 2017).

b. External Factors:

- Regulatory pressure

Regulations and policies that support sustainability can encourage organizations to adopt sustainable practices (Bowen et al., 2017).

- Industry norms and standards

Sustainability-focused industry norms and standards can provide guidance and framework for organizations (Prno & Slocombe, 2012).

- Market demand

Consumer and investor demand for sustainable products and services can encourage organizations to adopt sustainable practices (Alsayegh, 2020).

- Availability of technology

New technologies can help organizations to increase efficiency and reduce their environmental impact (Bolton & Hannon, 2016).

- Social and political context

A social and political context that supports sustainability can create an environment that is more conducive to the implementation of sustainability practices (Lange et al., 2013; Patterson et al., 2017).

- Stakeholder involvement

Active involvement of internal and external stakeholders in the sustainability governance process can increase accountability and legitimacy (Prno & Slocombe, 2012; Amran et al., 2013).

- Cooperation and collaboration

Cooperation and collaboration among organizations, governments, and civil society can help overcome complex sustainability challenges (Voegtlin & Scherer, 2017).

Governance and Sustainability: Discussion

Research on governance and sustainability highlights a variety of sometimes contrasting findings. Corporate governance mechanisms play an important role in various aspects of company performance. Hussain et al. (2018) find that certain governance mechanisms can influence profit, environmental and social performance differently. Michelon & Parbonetti (2012) confirmed that a good composition of the board of directors can increase a company's sustainability disclosure, while Albitar et al. (2018) found that companies that implement integrated reporting tend to have better financial performance. Additionally, Klettner et al. (2014) show that a clear leadership structure regarding sustainability is evidence of its implementation.

Commitment to sustainability is also reflected in the composition of the board of directors. Naciti (2019) finds that diverse board composition and separation of the roles of chairman and

CEO are associated with higher corporate sustainability performance, while Glass et al. (2016) stated that companies with gender diverse leadership are more effective in implementing environmentally friendly strategies. Amran et al. (2013) highlighted the importance of corporate social responsibility values embedded in the company's vision and mission to improve the quality of sustainability reporting.

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Governance challenges and schemes are also a focus of research. Bowen et al. (2017) identified three governance challenges to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), while Voegtlin & Scherer (2017) emphasized the need for deliberation-based governance schemes to encourage responsible innovation. Patterson et al. (2017) highlight the need for a more robust framework for understanding transformation towards sustainability.

Holistic governance approaches are also gaining attention. Lange et al. (2013) emphasized the need for a multi-dimensional approach to understand the complexity of sustainable development governance. Baumgartner & Rauter (2016) discuss three complementary dimensions of strategic management to integrate sustainability issues into company activities and strategies. Frantzeskaki & Loorbach (2012) propose transition management as a governance approach that can overcome the tension between setting sustainability targets and governance efforts.

ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) disclosure is also the focus of research. Albitar et al. (2018) found a positive relationship between ESGD scores and company performance, while Alsayegh (2020) emphasized that good disclosure of ESG information has a positive effect on a company's economic, environmental and social sustainability performance. Buallay (2018) found a positive relationship between ESG disclosure and bank performance. Garcia et al. (2017) found that companies in sensitive industries have better environmental performance, and Xie et al. (2017) found that ESG information disclosure has a positive relationship with company efficiency at moderate disclosure levels. Future research is expected to develop theories explaining which dimensions of sustainability are more affected by corporate governance, as well as analyzing business models in a socio-technical context. Additionally, Patterson et al. (2017) suggest the need for research on developing more robust frameworks for understanding transformation towards sustainability.

Factors that have a significant relationship to Sustainability Governance

Based on the results of the study in Table 1, it highlights a number of factors that have a significant relationship with "sustainability governance", namely sustainable governance in the context of various aspects of sustainability, such as Economy, Social and Governance (ESG). Research by Hussain et al. (2018) show that corporate governance mechanisms have different influences on profit, environmental and social performance, with the need to develop more in-depth theory regarding which dimensions of sustainability are more influenced by corporate governance. Meanwhile, research by Prno & Slocombe (2012) highlights the importance of social permission from local communities in the mining sector as a factor influencing project sustainability, emphasizing the active role of communities in sustainability governance. In addition, Michelon & Parbonetti (2012) found that the composition of the board of directors influences a company's sustainability disclosure, indicating that good corporate governance can influence sustainability reporting practices.

In addition, there is research that highlights the relationship between Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) disclosure and company sustainability performance. For example, Alsayegh's (2020) research found that good disclosure of ESG information has a positive impact on a company's economic, environmental and social sustainability performance. Furthermore, research by Albitar et al. (2016) show a positive relationship between ESG scores and company performance, with corporate governance mechanisms influencing this relationship, especially in companies that implement integrated reporting. In addition, other factors such as a diverse composition of the board of directors (Naciti, 2019) and female leadership (Glass et al., 2016) also have an influence on the company's sustainability performance. In addition, a study by Bolton & Hannon (2016) highlights the importance of innovative business models in supporting the transformation of socio-technical systems towards sustainability, emphasizing the need for a systems-based approach in sustainability governance. All of this research underscores the complexity of the factors involved in sustainable governance and the importance of considering various dimensions in the development of sustainable strategies and policies.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research that has been described, it can be concluded that internal and external factors have a significant role in determining sustainability in corporate governance. The composition of the board of directors, visionary leadership, effective sustainability management, supportive organizational culture, and transparent information disclosure are some of the internal factors that influence sustainability. Meanwhile, regulatory pressure, industry norms, market demand, technology availability, social and political context, stakeholder involvement, and cooperation and collaboration are external factors that play a role in supporting sustainability.

Sustainability Governance plays an important role in integrating economic, social and environmental aspects into business strategies and company operations. A diverse board of directors committed to sustainability, strong leadership, and an organizational culture that supports sustainability are key internal factors that encourage sustainable decision making and increase corporate accountability. In addition, transparent and comprehensive Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) disclosure has been proven to have a positive relationship with a company's sustainability performance. The integration of sustainability into business strategy through strategic sustainability management approaches and the development of innovative business models is also essential. Furthermore, active stakeholder involvement and the development of deliberation-based governance schemes are necessary to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). However, there are significant challenges that need to be overcome, including in the development of more robust frameworks for understanding the transformation towards sustainability. This research provides practical recommendations for companies to strengthen the composition of their boards of directors, increase the transparency of ESG disclosures, adopt a strategic sustainability management approach, actively engage stakeholders, and overcome regulatory and political challenges to achieve better sustainability.

Suggestions for future research could include the development of theories that explain which dimensions of sustainability are more affected by corporate governance, as well as the analysis of business models in a socio-technical context. Research could also focus on developing more robust frameworks for understanding the transformation towards sustainability. In addition, further studies on ESG disclosure and its relationship with companies' economic, environmental and social sustainability performance are also needed. Limitations of the research that has been conducted include challenges in achieving sustainable development goals (SDGs) and strengthening existing reference frameworks. In addition, there is still a need to improve the quality of sustainability reporting in various regions, as has been revealed in related research. Therefore, future research needs to pay attention to these challenges to be able to provide more comprehensive insights into sustainability governance practices and strategies.

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